

COMS14 A and COMS15 A–CMS lines from popular rice varieties of Tamil Nadu, India, with good grain quality

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Hybrid varieties, developed by making use of wild abortive (WA)-type cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines, accounted for approximately 90% of all hybrid rice produced in China in the past. These hybrids have significantly outyielded conventional pure-line cultivars (Yuan 1994). As the WA cytoplasm was found to be the most stable, about 95% of rice hybrids in the world are based on this single source of cyto sterility (Virmani 1998). The major constraint to the popularization of hybrid rice in India is its poor grain quality, though the yield potential is more than 20% higher than that of inbred varieties. Developing new CMS lines in the background of agronomically adapted and popular varieties is the need of the hour. ADT43, a derivative of IR50/Improved White Ponni, is a short-duration and popular variety with good grain quality. It is best grown in the May-June and December-January seasons in all districts of Tamil Nadu. Another variety, CO 47, a short-duration variety derived from IR50/CO 43, is also widely cultivated by farmers. ADT43 and CO 47 were crossed with IR69616 A and IR58025 A, respectively, to develop new hybrid combinations. These were then evaluated in a test-cross nursery during the 2000 kharif season. The hybrids – IR58025 A/CO 47 and IR69616 A/ADT43 – showed a maintainer reaction with 100% pollen sterility at the flowering stage. The two male parents, CO 47 and ADT43, were used as recurrent parents in the backcrossing program. New CMS lines developed through substitution backcrossing have been reported by Ingale et al (2004) and Manonmani et al (2006). After repeated backcrossing of six generations (rabi 2003), two new CMS lines – COMS14 A (IR69616 A/ADT43) (Fig. 1) and COMS15 A (IR58025 A/CO 47) (Fig. 2) were developed with better floral characteristics. The characteristics of these lines are given in the table. These new lines can be exploited to develop medium slender rice hybrids with good grain quality.

Fig 1. COMS14 A.

Fig 2. COMS15 A.

Characteristics of COMS14 A and COMS15 A.

Character	COMS14A	COMS15A
Early plant vigor	Good	Good
Coleoptile	Green	Green
Basal leaf sheath color	Green	Green
Leaf blade color	Light green	Light green
Leaf pubescence	Intermediate	Intermediate
Leaf length (cm)	33	31
Leaf width (mm)	0.9	1.3
Stem color	Green	Green
Auricles	Present curved	Present curved
Liquile	Prominent	Prominent
Days to 50% flowering	85.0	90.0
Panicle exertion (%)	70.7	75.7
Stigma color	White	White
Apiculus color	Straw	Straw
Effective tillers (no.)	9.0	9.4
Plant height (cm)	74.0	96.4
Panicle length (cm)	20.4	21.4
Panicle type	Compact	Compact
Awning	Nil	Nil
Days to maturity	110–115	120
Seedcoat color	Light brown	Light brown
Grain length-breadth ratio	2.8	3.3
100-grain weight (g)	1.5	1.6
Hull color (husk color)	Straw	Straw
Threshability	Easy	Easy
Aroma	Absent	Absent
Pollen fertility (%)	0	0

References

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